

CHAPTER 4

Inorganic lead-free Cs₂GeSnCl₆ double perovskite absorber and SnO₂ hole blocking layer with 16.35 % efficiency

In this article, we have explored a new lead-free halide double perovskite named as Cs₂GeSnCl₆. The main motivation of this study is to predict and optimize the photovoltaic efficiency of lead-free halide based single junction solar cell with Cs₂GeSnCl₆ as an absorbing layer. We have discussed about structural, electronic, optical and thermoelectric properties of Cs₂GeSnCl₆. In first section, the structural properties such as crystal structure, lattice parameter, tolerance factor, octahedral factor and bond angle are calculated. In the next, thermodynamic stability of Cs₂GeSnCl₆ is investigated by calculating its formation energy along with phonon band structure. Thereafter, the electronic properties such as band structure and density of states of Cs₂GeSnCl₆ is discussed. Then we have discussed in details about the optical properties of Cs₂GeSnCl₆. Finally, we modelled Cs₂GeSnCl₆ based single junction solar cell with SnO₂ hole-blocking layer. The power conversion efficiency (PCE%) of this solar cell is optimized as a function of absorber layer thickness, SnO₂ layer thickness, defect density and temperature. The optimized PCE % of constructed solar cell is around 16.35% which is higher than the previous value obtained from other lead-free halide double perovskite based solar cell.

4.2 Computational details

The structural, electronic, optical and thermoelectric properties of title compounds were calculated by using Wien2k simulation package [83]. The DFT is considered as one of the most precise tools to explain the electronic, thermoelectric and optoelectronic properties of solid . The structural properties were investigated with the help of GGA-PBE exchange correlation. On the other hand, GGA-PBE+ mBJ + SOC is found to one of most precise to predict the electronic and optical properties of lead-free double perovskites with high accuracy [85]. The plane wave cut off was set to be 8 ($K_{\max} * R_{MT} = 8.0$). We considered a k mesh of 10 x 10 x 10 for the electronic studies of Cs₂GeSnCl₆. The above input parameters provided us the convergence level of 10⁻⁵ Ry self consistently. Since, the accuracy optical properties are

dependent k-point sampling. Therefore, we have considered a higher k mesh of 20000 to calculate the same. Furthermore, we have employed one dimensional solar capacitance simulator (SCAPS-1D) to investigate the photovoltaic properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ base solar cell i.e., ITO/ SnO_2 / $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ /Au [81, 82]. We have optimized important material parameter such as absorber layer ($\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$) thickness, hole-blocking layer (SnO_2), temperature, bulk defect density which give rise to the maximum PCE (%) of $\sim 16.35\%$.

4.2.1 Structural properties

$\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is stable in cubic phase with $\text{Fm}\bar{3}\text{m}$ (No. 225). The crystal structure of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is presented in figure 4.1. It is noticeable from figure 4.1 that $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is showing a network of corner sharing octahedra with monovalent Cs^+ located at the middle of octahedral cavity. Each Cs^+ is coordinated with 12 Cl whereas every Ge^+ and Sn^{3+} cations are surrounded by 6 Cl ions. It is also evident from figure 4.1 that GeCl_6 and SnCl_6 octahedra are alternatively arranged in the direction of $[1\ 0\ 0]$, $[0\ 1\ 0]$ and $[0\ 0\ 1]$. The center of each octahedra is either occupied Ge^+ or Sn^{3+} in alternating configuration. The Wyckoff positions for Cs^+ , Ge^+ , Sn^{3+} , and Cl^- are found to at $(0.25, 0.25, 0.25)$, $(0, 0, 0)$, $(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$ and $(0.25, 0, 0)$ respectively.

Figure 4.1: The crystal structure of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$.

For stable cubic phase, τ should be in the range of 0.9 -1.02 [95]. Fortunately, the τ value of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is found to be in the above-mentioned range which demonstrates its stability in cubic phase.

$$\mu = \frac{R_B}{R_X} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\tau = 0.707 \frac{(R_A+R_X)}{(R_B+R_X)} \quad (4.2)$$

4.2.2 Mechanical properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$

The mechanical stability of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ was examined from elastic constant values (C_{ij}) obtained by using Cubic Elastic package [66]. To obtain this, the cubic crystal structures were deformed by applying small strain. We have noticed that the deformed structure has higher energy than equilibrium for both systems. It is also noticeable that the titled system was perfectly obeyed Born criteria of mechanical stability i.e., $C_{11} - C_{12} > 0$, $C_{44} > 0$, $C_{11} + 2C_{12} > 0$, $C_{12} < B < C_{11}$ [96]. Furthermore, we have obtained the positive Cauchy's pressure (CP= $C_{12} - C_{44}$) value which indicates the ductile nature of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$.

To investigate the thermal stability of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$, we have calculated formation energy which is given by

$$H_f = E_{Total} - lE_{Cl} - mE_{Ge} - nE_{Cs} - oE_{Sn} \quad (4.3)$$

Where, E_{Total} , E_{Cl} , E_{Ge} , E_{Cs} , and E_{Sn} are the energies of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$, Br, Ge, Cs and Sn respectively. The negative H_f value of -2.63 confirmed the thermodynamic stability of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$. Furthermore, we have investigated the phonon spectra of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ which is shown in figure 4.2. We have noticed from Fig. 4.2 that no imaginary phonon frequencies exist throughout the Brillouin zone for both systems. Thus, $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is predicted to be a dynamically stable system.

Figure 4.2: The phonon dispersion band structure of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$.

Table 4.1 Computed lattice parameter (a), tolerance factor (τ), and formation energy (H_f), bulk modulus (B), Elastic constants (C_{ij}), Cauchy pressure (CP), and formation energy values of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$.

Systems	a (Å)	τ	B (GPa)	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	CP	H_f (eV)
$\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$	10.53	0.96	24.17	49.31	11.78	9.17	2.61	-2.63

4.2.3 Electronic band structure of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$

The electronic properties of a system can be investigated from its band structure analysis. It helps to predict whether the system is semiconductor or metal or insulator. In addition to this, many physical properties such as properties can also be understood from the band structure profile. Therefore, the band structure of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is evaluated by GA-PBE + mBJ and GA-PBE + mBJ + SOC approaches as shown in figure 4.3 (a) and figure 4.3 (b), respectively. It is noticeable from figure 4.3 (a) and figure 4.3 (b) that the valance band maxima (VBM) and conduction band minima (CBM) are located at same K-point indicating the direct band gap nature of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$. The band gap values of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ using different approaches are noticed to be 1.22 eV (GA-PBE + mBJ) and 0.93 eV (with GA-PBE + mBJ + SOC). It is

important to be mentioned here that GA-PBE + mBJ + SOC approach can predict the accurate band gap of lead-free double perovskites. Also, GA-PBE + mBJ + SOC showed that the band gap of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is within the required range i.e., 0.9 -1.6 eV for high efficiency solar cell. Thus, $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is predicted to be a suitable photovoltaic material.

Figure 4.3: The band structure of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ obtained with (a) GA-PBE + mBJ, and (b) GA-PBE + mBJ + SOC.

4.2.4 Density of states of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$

To clarify the band structure results, we have calculated the density of states (DOS) of titled compound. The DOS result is shown in figure 5.4. It is evident from figure 4.4 that band in range from -4 eV to 0 eV is mainly occupied by Ge-s state whereas conduction state from 0.93 to 4 eV is mainly occupied by Sn-p orbital.

Figure 4.4: The density of states of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ obtained with GA-PBE + mBJ + SOC.

4.2.5 Photovoltaic properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$

The lead-free double perovskites are known to have strong optical absorption coefficient due to their outstanding electronic properties such as large dielectric constant, tuneable band gap etc. Therefore, lead free double perovskites are preferable candidate for the construction of high efficiency solar cell. Motivated by the direct band gap value of 0.93 eV, we have calculated the optical properties of Cs₂GeSnCl₆. It is important to be mentioned here that the optical properties such as conductivity, absorption coefficient, and reflectivity can be derived from frequency dependent complex dielectric function, $\varepsilon(\omega)$. The $\varepsilon(\omega)$ demonstrates the response of a material when it is subjected to external EM radiation. The $\varepsilon(\omega)$ can be represented as

$$\varepsilon(\omega) = \varepsilon_1(\omega) + i\varepsilon_2(\omega) \quad (4.4)$$

The imaginary part of $\varepsilon_2(\omega)$ can be expressed as

$$\varepsilon_2(\omega) = \frac{8}{2\pi\omega^2} * \sum P_{nn'}^2 \frac{dS_k}{\nabla\omega_{nn'}} \quad (4.5)$$

The real dielectric constant $\varepsilon_1(\omega)$ can be obtained by using Kramer's- Kronig relation

$$\varepsilon_1(\omega) = \frac{2}{\pi} * \int_0^\alpha \omega' \varepsilon_2(\omega) \frac{d\omega'}{(\omega^2 - \omega'^2)} \quad (4.6)$$

The real dielectric constant $\varepsilon_1(\omega)$ determine the polarization of light. Also, $\varepsilon_1(\omega)$ demonstrate the energy deposited by EM wave while it is passing through the medium. The $\varepsilon_1(\omega)$ is presented in figure 4.5(a), which shows the static dielectric i.e., $\varepsilon_1(0)$ is about 4.5. The appreciable value of $\varepsilon_1(0)$ demonstrated their defect tolerance capability of this system. Also, it is noticeable that $\varepsilon_1(\omega)$ is positive in the entire energy range implies its capability to retain semiconducting nature. The absorption of a system can be explained by $\varepsilon_2(\omega)$ as shown in figure 4.5(b). The threshold energy of absorption is found to be 0.97 eV, which is known as optical band gap. It is interesting to be mentioned that the optical band gap is close to its electronic band gap of Cs₂GeSnCl₆. The absorption coefficient (α) explained the photon harvesting capability of a system. In fact, the photovoltaic performance can be predicted from the value of α of absorbing layer. The α spectra of Cs₂GeSnCl₆ is shown Figure 4.4 (b). It is evident from Figure 4.4 (b) that the higher order (10^5 cm^{-1}) absorption coefficient beyond the optical band gap of Cs₂GeSnCl₆. Also, the first peak of α is noticed to be at 2.71 eV which is may be due to electronic transition from Ge-s to Sn-p orbitals of Cs₂GeSnCl₆. Furthermore,

figure 4.5(b) shows that there is a rapid increment of α beyond the photon energy value of 3.91 eV. The optical conductivity (σ) demonstrates the conduction capability of charge carrier when photon having certain energy fall into the material. The σ spectra of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is shown in figure 4.5(c). The maximum σ is found to be $1910 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 2.73 eV. It is important to be mentioned here that $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ has higher σ compared than the recently predicted optical conductivity of $\text{Cs}_2\text{NaGaBr}_6$. Similar to α , the value σ increases rapidly beyond the incoming photon energy value of 3.91 eV. We have also studied the reflectivity (R) property of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$. It is evident from figure 4.5(d) that the value of R at zero frequency is around 11.9 %. The maximum R is noticed to be 13.1 % at 2.01 eV. Altogether, the high α , σ and low R implying $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is a emerging photovoltaic material.

Figure 4.5: The optical properties (a) Real and imaginary dielectric constants, (b) Absorption coefficient, (c) Optical conductivity, and (d) Reflectivity of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$.

4.2.6 Single junction solar cell device simulation

The schematic representation of charge flow across ITO/ $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ /SnO₂/Au heterojunction is shown in figure 5.6 (b). Also, the photovoltaic performance of above-mentioned cell is predicted by using SCAPS-1D simulation package. Also, the working steps of SCAPS-1D is

shown in figure 4.6 (c). In addition, the input parameters used for this simulation are shown in table. 4.2.

Figure 4.6: The schematic representation of (a) charge flow across ITO/Cs₂GeSnCl₆/SnO₂/Au, (b) structure of ITO/Cs₂GeSnCl₆/SnO₂/Au solar cell and (c) working steps of SCAPS-1D.

The conduction (N_c) and valance band (N_v) density of states can be calculated by using following equations [97]

$$N_c = \frac{2[2\pi m_e K_B T]^{1.5}}{h^{1.5}} \quad (4.7)$$

$$N_v = \frac{2[2\pi m_h K_B T]^{1.5}}{h^{1.5}} \quad (4.8)$$

4.1 Computed lattice parameter (a), tolerance factor (τ), and formation energy (H_f), bulk modulus (B), Elastic constants (C_{ij}), Cauchy pressure (CP), and formation energy values of Cs₂GeSnCl₆.

Table 4.2 The materials parameters used for SCAPS-1D simulation.

Parameters	SnO ₂ [98]	Cs ₂ GeSnCl ₆
Band gap(eV)	3.5	0.93
Electron Affinity (eV)	4	3.94
Dielectric permittivity (ϵ_r)	9	4.13
Thickness (nm)	Varied	Varied
CB effective density of State (cm ⁻³)	2.2x10 ¹⁷	2.23 x10 ¹⁸
VB effective density of State (cm ⁻³)	2.2x10 ¹⁶	5.1 x10 ¹⁸
Electron mobility (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	20	10
Hole mobility (cm ² V ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	10	10
Donor density, ND (cm ⁻³)	1x10 ¹⁸	1x10 ¹⁰
Acceptor density, NA (cm ⁻³)	-----	1x10 ¹⁰

During synthesis of perovskite halide, the unintentional surface defect is generated at the interface of the device. Thus, the influence of defect density on the PCE (%) of above-mentioned solar cell is examined. It is important to be mentioned here that the lead-free double halides perovskite materials have high defect tolerance limit compared to other photovoltaic materials. The deep defects of 10¹⁴ - 10¹⁶ cm⁻³ and shallow defects of 10¹⁰ – 10¹¹ cm⁻³ are usually dominated in conventional solar cells. Also, the shallow defect has no significant influence on PCE (%) [99]. But, the deep defect acts as a charge recombination center which can reduce the PCE (%) of a solar cell. Usually, MAPbI₃ shows the deep defect density of 0.65 and 0.76 eV below the conduction band edge. But due to lack of report on defect density of Cs₂GeSnCl₆, we kept the constant value as MAPbI₃. The carrier mobility (μ) of Cs₂AgBiBr₆ and other perovskite halides are different [100]. For Cs₂GeSnCl₆, the carrier mobility is calculated by using following equation

$$\mu = \frac{e\tau}{m^*} \quad (4.9)$$

where e , τ and m^* represent the electronic charge, relaxation time and effective mass of a carrier. The obtained values electron mobility (μ_e) and hole mobility (μ_h) values are $10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ S}^{-1}$ and $10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ S}^{-1}$ for $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$. The electron affinity (χ) of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is varied and found to be 3.94 eV , which is lower than the value predicted by Kale et al. for $\text{Cs}_2\text{AuBiCl}_6$ [101].

The hole blocking nature of SnO_2 is investigated from barrier potential calculation. The electron and hole barrier potential *i.e.* ΔE_c and ΔE_v can be calculated as follows

$$\Delta E_c = \chi(\text{SnO}_2) - \chi(\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6) \quad (4.10)$$

$$\Delta E_v = E_g(\text{SnO}_2) + \Delta E_c - E_g(\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6) \quad (4.11)$$

Where χ and E_g represent the electron affinity and band gap of corresponding system. The obtained ΔE_c and ΔE_v values are summarized in table 4.3. It is noticeable from table 2 that $\Delta E_v > \Delta E_c$ implies that the SnO_2 works as a hole-blocking layer for $\text{SnO}_2/\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ heterojunction. The band bending diagram of $\text{SnO}_2/\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSn}_6$ is shown in figure 5.7.

Table 4.3 The calculated values of ΔE_c (eV) and ΔE_v (eV) of $\text{SnO}_2/\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ interface.

Interface	ΔE_c (ev)	ΔE_v (ev)
$\text{SnO}_2/\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$	0.06	2.54

Figure 4.7: The band bending diagram of SnO₂/Cs₂GeSnCl₆ interface.

In order to get maximum PCE (%), first of all we have optimized absorbing layer thickness. The PCE (%) versus absorbing layer thickness curve is shown in figure 4.8 (a). It is evident from figure 5.8 (a) that there is a rapid increment of PCE (%) at initial stage but it becomes constant above the thickness value 1.2 μm. This PCE (%) features can be explained from Beer-Lamberts law, $I = I_0 e^{-\alpha x}$. The optimized absorbing layer thickness showed the maximum PCE (%) 16.35 %. The effects of SnO₂ thickness on PCE (%) is also studied which is shown in figure 5.8 (b). It is noticeable from figure 4.8 (b) PCE (%) decreases with SnO₂ thickness which is may be due to the increase of resistant value of the device. The effect of bulk defect density on PCE (%) is also studied which is shown in figure 4.8 (c). The bulk defect density acts as a charge recombination centre which can reduce the device performance. To investigate this, we have varied it from 10¹² to 10¹⁸ cm⁻³. It is clearly noticeable from figure 4.8 (c) that the performance of the device is severely affected by defect density beyond 10¹⁵ cm⁻³. However, it is always recommended that the bulk defect density should be much below the critical limit. The working temperature play a crucial role to govern the PCE (%). Although, the testing

temperature of a solar cell always kept at 300 K but during installation the device temperature may change. Thus, we have studied the effect of temperature on device performance. Figure 5.8 (d) revealed the decrease of PCE (%) decrease linearly with temperature. The temperature rising leads to the creation of stress and deformation inside the photovoltaic cell. The creation of stress and deformation may lead to the decrease of PCE (%). Thus, one should maintain the device temperature around 300 K.

Figure 4.8: The Effect of (a) absorber layer thickness, (b) SnO₂ thickness, (c) bulk defect density and (d) temperature on the PCE (%) of ITO/Cs₂GeSnCl₆/SnO₂/Au solar cell.

Finally, J-V and EQE curves are studied with optimized values of absorbing layer thickness, buffer layer thickness, temperature, bulk defect density etc. figure 4.9 (a) presented the J-V curve computed for ITO/Cs₂GeSnCl₆/SnO₂/Au solar cell by using the input parameters discussed in Table 1. Also, we have studied the external quantum efficiency (EQE) of the device as shown in figure 4.9 (b). The EQE is found to be 73 % at 300 nm and then achieved quickly to the apex of 87 % at 330 nm. Beyond this limit, the EQE is found to be almost constant up to 870 nm and then it decreases rapidly and drop down to zero at 900 nm. The output parameters from J-V curve are summarized in table 4.4 . It is important to be mentioned here that our obtained PCE (%) is much higher than the recently predicted value for

$\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ based solar cell [102]. The obtained higher efficiency is due to direct band gap value 0.93 eV of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$. Also, obtained ΔE_c is much smaller.

Figure 4.9: (a) J vs V spectrum and (b) EQE spectrum of ITO/ $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ /SnO₂/Au solar cell.

Table 4.4 Simulated results of J -V curve

Structure	J_{sc} (mA cm ⁻²)	V_{oc} (V)	FF	PCE (%)
ITO/ $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ /SnO ₂ /Au	26.35	1.02	0.73	16.35

4.3 Summary and Conclusion

In this chapter, we have studied the structural, electronic, optical and photovoltaic properties of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ by first-principles and SCAPS-1D simulations. The thermodynamic stability of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ is confirmed from its negative formation energy and absence of imaginary phonon frequency. The obtained electronic band gap is noticed to be 0.93 eV (with GGA-PBE + mBJ + SOC) which is within the required range of 0.9 eV -1.6 eV, for the construction of high efficiency solar cell. Furthermore, the outshining optical properties such as higher order (10^5 cm^{-1}) of absorption coefficient, appreciable conductivity, and low reflectivity are resulted from dispersed direct band of $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$. The photovoltaic study showed the maximum PCE (%) of 16.35 % for ITO/ $\text{Cs}_2\text{GeSnCl}_6$ /SnO₂/Au heterojunction, which is much higher than the recently predicted value from $\text{Cs}_2\text{AgBiBr}_6$ based solar cell. Thus, we believe that this study

will provide guidelines for the construction of lead-free double perovskite based high efficiency solar cell.